

The Impact of Organisational Support and Organisational Identification on the Job Performance of University Staff

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of perceived organisational support (POS) and organisational identification (OI) on job performance among university staff. The research was conducted using a cross-sectional design, with data collected from 164 staff members of the University of Cape Coast through structured questionnaires. Findings indicate that 90.2% of staff perceive moderate levels of organisational support. However, the study found no direct relationship between POS and job performance ($r = .077$, $p = .326$). Instead, organisational identification emerged as a significant predictor of job performance ($r = .458$, $p < .001$). A weak but significant correlation between POS and OI ($r = .156$, $p = .046$) was observed. Multiple regression analysis further confirmed that OI significantly predicts job performance ($\beta = .827$, $p < .001$), while POS does not have a significant impact ($\beta = .013$, $p = .900$). The overall model explains 21.1% of the variance in job performance ($R^2 = .211$, $F(3,160) = 14.248$, $p < .001$), emphasising that OI plays a stronger role in predicting employee performance than POS. The study underscores the importance of strengthening organisational identification as a more effective strategy for improving employee performance than simply increasing perceived support. Recommendations include enhancing

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organisational identification through leadership initiatives, participatory decision-making, and a strong workplace culture. Additionally, professional development opportunities, fair treatment, and recognition programmes can help improve POS and indirectly influence job performance.

Keywords: *Higher Education Institutions, Job Performance, Organisational Identification, Perceived Organisational Support, Professional development and University of Cape Coast.*

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Introduction

Performance is considered an essential element in managing organisations worldwide where outcomes are compared with overall organisational goals and objectives (Akpa et al., 2021). Organisations have to focus extensively on the performance of employees to enhance their capabilities and for the achievement of goals (Zhenjing et al., 2022). Organisations have considered employees as strategic assets and have begun to invest in employee development programmes. Employees show greater commitment towards the organisation in terms of heightened performance and less likelihood of quitting the job (Yandi & Havidz, 2022). Some employees in organisations enjoy facilities like daycare, meals, a gym and transportation to and from work and they are encouraged to spend 20% of their time pursuing their ideas. In these ways, the organisation communicates that it values employees' contributions (Norouzi & Angel, 2023).

The norm of reciprocity prescribes that “people should help those who have helped them and that people should not injure those who have helped them” (Kotowski, 2020). To the extent that both parties apply the norm of reciprocity to their relationship, it would benefit both. In the employment context, social exchange theory emphasises that the interacting parties (employee and employer) exchange effort and loyalty for tangible benefits and social rewards. The organisational support theory supposes that employees create global beliefs that their organisation will reward their extra effort and meet their socio-emotional needs, which is termed as perceived organisational support (POS) (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Therefore, perceived organisational support is an assurance that organisation would be involved in activities to help employees to carry out the job effectively. Important outcomes of perceived organisational support are job performance (Karatepe, 2012), employee physical health (Arnold & Dupre, 2012) and organisational commitment (Arshadi, 2011). Among the outcomes of perceived organisational support, is job performance which is measured through in-role performance and extra-role performance.

Perceived organisational support has been defined as the value contributions, and recognition given to employees by organisations (Mascarenhas et al., 2022). It is also the organisational mindset for valuing the efforts of workers and care for employee well-being. Various factors combine to form perceived organisational support which includes working conditions, positive behaviour and attitude of employees and human resources management practices (Karatepe et al., 2022). Equal and fair treatment at the workplace among employees for rewards and favourable working conditions which are supported by management and the strategic apex who was found to be positively associated with perceived organisational support (Chillakuri & Vanka, 2022). On the other hand, the efforts of employees at the workplace are reinforced by perceived organisational support and the consequence was found to be the achievement of goals.

Organisational identification, which refers to the psychological attachment between an individual and his or her work organisation, has captured the attention of organisational theorists and practitioners during the last decade because of the positive effects that it has been shown to have on various work outcomes (Akpa et al., 2021). For example, studies have indicated that higher identification leads to enhanced job

performance, lower absenteeism and turnover rates, more extra-role behaviours, greater job satisfaction, increased motivation and improved health and physical well-being (Kim et al., 2023; Roodbol & Stynen, 2023). Given this evidence, it is reasonable to expect that increased identification can play a pivotal role in augmenting organisational efficiency and effectiveness.

Organisational identification is a particular form of social identification in which individuals categorise themselves as members of an organisation (Schwarz, 2017). Organisational identification can be defined as the 'perception of oneness with or belongingness to an organisation' (Sammarra et al., 2021). Individuals identify strongly with an organisation if their organisational membership is more salient than alternative identities and if their self-concept features attributes that they ascribe to their organisation (Caprar et al., 2022).

Perceived organisational support and organisational identification influence work-related and job performance outcomes. Organisations must focus extensively on the performance of employees to enhance their capabilities and achievement of goals (Chen, 2017). Therefore, the performance of employees in an educational institution emerges as an important factor. Previously, various studies explained multiple reasons for dropped performance such as lack of organisational support, recent studies found an influence of perceived organisational support on performance (Khan, 2015).

University employees' effectiveness is crucial to delivering high-quality instruction, progressing research, and smoothing administrative processes in modern higher education institutions. Perceived organisational support (POS) and organisational identity (OI) significantly impact employee motivation, engagement, and performance. Workers who believe their organisations are providing them with a lot of assistance are typically more engaged, dedicated, and effective. On the other hand, people who feel unsupported could experience disengagement, burnout, and job discontent. Universities still face difficulties with staff turnover, low work satisfaction, and weakened organisational commitment, all of which have a negative impact on institutional effectiveness, even though there is a growing body of research addressing these issues (Dinc et al, 2022).

According to research, perceived organisational support (POS) helps to improve organisational identity (OI), which in turn improves job performance (Druye et al. 2024). However, not enough research has been done to determine how much OI influences the connection between performance and perceived support in academic settings (Champika, 2024). Hence, this paper examined the influence of organisational support and organisational identification of employees on job performance.

This paper would provide useful information on how organisational support and organisation identification affects the job performance of staff at the University of Cape Coast and measures needed to improve staff performance at their workplace.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of organisational support of staff of University of Cape Coast?
2. What is the relationship between organisational support, organisational identification and job performance among staff of the University of Cape Coast?
3. What is the impact of organisational support and organisational identification on job performance of staff of University of Cape Coast?

Theoretical Background

Organisational Support Theory

According to the organisational support theory, fortunate opportunities for rewards help to communicate a confident valuation of employees' assistance and thus fund perceived organisational support (POS) (Arokiasamy et al., 2010). Favourable HR practices that indicate an investment in human assets and demonstrate gratitude for employee contributions have remained suggested to encourage POS (Serenko, 2023). Employees are notified of how co-workers are treated based on their opinion of organisational support (Kotowski, 2020). Perceived organisational support is perceived as work-group maintenance,

which is a distinct idea (Self et al., 2005). A strong evidence of this give-and-take relationship is found in organisational support theory (Eisenberger et al., 2017). Activities that demonstrate over-commitment to the organisation reflect employees reciprocating organisational support. Workers feel a sense of identification (Knippenberg & Sleebos, 2006) and a sense of self-importance (Fuller et al., 2006) in their organisation.

Social Identity Theory

In social identity theory, a social identity is a person's knowledge that he or she belongs to a social category or group (Hogg 2016). A social group is a set of individuals who hold a common social identification or view themselves as members of the same social category. Through a social comparison process, people who are similar to the self are categorised with the self and are labelled the in-group; people who differ from the self are categorised as the out-group. In early work, social identity included the emotional, evaluative, and other psychological correlates of in-group classification (Devine, 2015). Later researchers often separated the self-categorisation component from the self-esteem (evaluative) and commitment (psychological) components to empirically investigate the relationships among them. The two important processes involved in social identity formation, namely self-categorisation and social comparison, produce different consequences (Hogg & Abrams, 1988). The consequence of self-categorisation is an accentuation of the perceived similarities between the self and other in-group members and an accentuation of the perceived differences between the self and out-group members. This accentuation occurs for all the attitudes, beliefs and values, affective reactions, behavioural norms, styles of speech, and other properties that are believed to be correlated with the relevant intergroup categorisation. The consequence of the social comparison process is the selective application of the evaluation effect, primarily to those dimensions that will result in self-enhancing outcomes for the self. Specifically, one's self-esteem is enhanced by evaluating the in-group and the out-group on dimensions that lead the in-group to be judged positively and the out-group to be judged negatively. As Hogg and Abrams (1988) posited social categories in which individuals place themselves are parts of a structured society and exist only with other contrasting categories (for example, black vs. white); each has more or less power, prestige, status, and so on. Further, these authors point out that the social categories precede individuals; individuals are born into an already structured society. Once in society, people derive their identity or sense of self largely from the social categories to which they belong. Each person, however, throughout his or her personal history, is a member of a unique combination of social categories; therefore, the set of social identities making up that person's self-concept is unique.

Social identity theory maintains that an individual's self-concept consists of a personal and social component and that individuals order their social environment by categorising people into groups (Asgari et al. 2008). Individuals identify with social categories due to a desire for safety and uncertainty reduction and to enhance their self-esteem. This identification enables them to partake in the successes of a group whose accomplishments are beyond their individualistic powers (Haslam, et al. 2020). Organisational identification is a particular form of social identification in which individuals categorise themselves as members of an organisation (Schwarz, 2017).

Individuals identify strongly with an organisation if their organisational membership is more salient than alternative identities and if their self-concept features attributes they ascribe to their organisation (Dutton & Dukerich, 1991). Strong organisational identification can translate into favourable outcomes, such as greater employee compliance and job satisfaction (Haslam et al 2020). However, strong identification can also lead to stress and depression when the employing organisation is confronted with external criticism (Dutton & Dukerich, 1991). While this research demonstrates that organisational identification is a powerful concept that facilitates the understanding of employee behaviours in the wider literature, Rho et al. (2015) argued that 'the role of inside members' image and identification has been ignored in public and non-profit management research' and should be analysed in more detail. Civil servants may possess high levels of organisational identification if they believe that their public agency is similarly motivated to serve the public good. Therefore, organisational identification offers a unique perspective to examine the job performance relationship (Akila & Priyadarshini, 2018).

Level of Perceived Organisational Support of University Staff

Many studies have investigated the perceptions of faculty and administrative staff regarding organisational support and how these perceptions influence workplace behaviour, academic output, and institutional loyalty. The research findings indicate that elevated levels of perceived organisational support (POS) are associated with positive workplace behaviour, heightened motivation, and decreased turnover. In contrast, insufficient levels of support correlate with increased workplace stress, dissatisfaction, and disengagement. For example, academic staff at Eastern University in Sri Lanka reported a high level of POS, which was positively correlated with job satisfaction (Judge et al 2020). Similarly, staff at Al-Aqsa University in Gaza recognised a significant degree of organisational support, which was linked to enhanced organisational confidence and citizenship behaviour (Hashish, 2018). Conversely, administrative personnel at newly established universities in China indicated slightly lower levels of POS, which adversely impacted their job performance and work engagement (Wan & Saidin, 2018; Hassan et al., 2021). Furthermore, research indicates that when perceived organisational support is excessively high or low, employees who experience organisational cynicism exhibit diminished performance. Conversely, when perceived organisational support is moderate, employees exhibiting organisational cynicism tend to demonstrate improved performance (Byrne & Hochwarter, 2008). This variability in POS levels suggests a dependence on the university's establishment status and administrative focus.

Relationship between Organisational Support, Organisational Identification and Job Performance among University Staff

Perceived organisational support has shown a moderate, positive relationship with job performance (Riggle, Edmondson & Hansen, 2009). It showed a positive association with work performance and organisational citizenship behaviour (Miao & Kim, 2010; Rich, Lepine & Crawford, 2010). Perceived organisational support from the parent company and the subsidiary is positively related to expatriates' organisational citizenship behaviour (Liu, 2009). Perceived organisational support showed an insignificant, indirect relationship with job performance through social exchange with organisation (Byrne et al., 2011). Perceived organisational support showed a positive relationship with athletic performance (Rocha & Chelladurai, 2011). It is found that perceived organisational support is positively related to temporal changes in performance, while the reverse relationship is found to be insignificant (Chen et al., 2009). In addition, it is found that perceived organisational support increases service recovery performance among hotel employees (Karatepe, 2012). Using a cross-lagged panel design, perceived organisational support is found to be related to a change in extra-role performance (Chen et al., 2009).

Organisational identification (OI) is positively associated with job performance. This relationship is evident across various studies, showing that when university staff feel a strong connection to their institution, their performance improves (Ting & Ho, 2017; Thanh et al., 2022; Issa et al., 2022) OI can act as a moderating variable, enhancing the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. It also serves as a mediator in the relationship between leader-member exchange and job performance, indicating that strong identification with the organisation can enhance the effects of positive leader-member relationships on performance (Thanh et al., 2022; Issa et al., 2022)

Impact of Organisational Support and Organisational Identification on Job Performance of University Staff

Organisational support and identification significantly impact the job performance of university staff. Perceived organisational support (POS) is consistently linked to improved job performance, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment among university staff, while organisational identification (OI) enhances employee performance through increased job satisfaction and commitment. For instance, POS is positively correlated with job performance among university staff. Studies indicate that higher levels of perceived organisational support lead to better job performance, although factors like job satisfaction and affective commitment can mediate the effect (Wan & Saidin, 2018; Guan et al., 2014). Kazmi and Javaid (2022) posited that organisational identification significantly influences employee performance by fostering a sense of belonging and commitment to the organisation.

Methodology

The study used a cross-sectional design, which collects data from many different individuals at a single point in time. The study's target population comprised all staff of the University of Cape Coast. The accessible population was a total of 300 staff from the halls of residence namely Casely Hayford Hall, Kwame Nkrumah Hall, Valco Hall, Adehye Hall, Oguaa Hall, Atlantic Hall, SRC Hall, and Superannuation Hall served as the theoretical population for this study. A total of 132 were males and 168 were females (Directorate of Human Resource, 2021). This group of staff were chosen because they were the most accessible to the researchers. Out of the 300 accessible population, a sample of 164 were selected. The sample was selected with reference to Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining the sample size of a population. The study revealed 96 (58.5%) were males and 68 (41.5%), females. This implies more males participated in the study than females. Regarding age, the average age was 38. For marital status, the majority were married 87 (53%), followed by single individuals 65 (39.6%), while a smaller proportion were divorced 7 (4.3%) or widowed 5 (3%). In terms of work experience, the average working experience was 12 years. Simple random sampling was subsequently employed in distributing the questionnaire to respondents. This sampling technique was chosen due to its capacity to enhance both internal validity and external validity, ensuring that findings are reliable and generalisable to the broader population (Acharya et al 2013). The staff members of seven halls of the University of Cape Coast responded to a Likert scale questionnaire, which served as the data collection tool.

Instruments

Perceived Organisational Support Scale

The perceived Organizational Support (POS) Scale, developed by Eisenberger et al. (1997) was employed. The Scale consisted of 8 items with a 7-point Likert scale (e.g., 1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree). The POS Scale includes statements such as *"The organisation strongly considers my goals and values"* and *"The organisation cares about my well-being."* Cronbach's alpha is 0.90, indicating excellent internal consistency.

Organisational Identification Scale

The degree to which employees identify with their organisation was measured with the Organisational Identification Scale (Mael & Tetrick, 1992). With a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), the 6-item test evaluates employees' feelings of emotional connection, shared identity, belongingness and response to organisational criticism. For example, *"When someone criticises my organisation, it feels like a personal insult"* and *"My organisation's successes are my successes"* are examples. The reliability is strong (Cronbach's alpha > 0.80).

Job Performance Scale

The Job Performance Scale was employed. It has an 18-item Likert-scale measure that uses a 5-point Likert-type scale, from 1 "rarely" to 5 "always," to evaluate job performance across various occupations (Koopmans et al. (2013). Task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behaviour are the three main dimensions. Sample examples include, *"I manage my workload efficiently,"* *"I take the initiative when there is a problem at work,"* and *"I make mistakes that negatively affect my work."* This scale had Cronbach's alpha of 0.80. which means that it has a high internal consistency.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, various ethical standards were adhered to. Articles, journals, books, and other credible resources were properly cited to uphold academic integrity. Before distributing the questionnaires, the study's objectives were briefed to respondents. Measures were taken to protect their privacy and anonymity, with all identifying information maintained in strict confidence. Participation in the study was voluntary, granting respondents the autonomy to withdraw at any point without facing any repercussions. Furthermore, the selection of participants was conducted equitably, ensuring that no form of discrimination was present.

Results

Table 1. Group Statistics for Variables

Variable	Mean	SD
Perceived Organisational Support	30.95	6.27
Organisational Identification	21.41	5.02
Job performance	57.59	9.35

1. What is the Level of Perceived Organisational Support of Staff of University of Cape Coast?

Table 2. Level of Perceived Organisational Support

	Frequency	Percent
Low (8-23)	8	4.9
Moderate (24-39)	148	90.2
High (40-56)	8	4.9
Total	164	100.0

Results from Table 2 indicate that the majority (148) 90.2% of workers receive moderate organisational support. The mean of 30.95 falls in the score range of 24-39 which is moderate organisational support.

2. What is the Relationship between Organisational Support, Organisational Identification and Job Performance among Staff of the University of Cape Coast?

Table 3. Pearson Correlation

		Organisational support	Organisational identification	Job performance
Organisational support	Pearson Correlation	1	.156*	.077
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.046	.326
	N	164	164	164
Organisational identification	Pearson Correlation	.156*	1	.458**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.046		.000
	N	164	164	164
Job performance	Pearson Correlation	.077	.458**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.326	.000	
	N	164	164	164

Results from Table 3 show a positive relationship between organisational identification and job performance $r(163) = .458, p < .001$. However, there was no relationship between organisational support and job performance but a positive relationship between organisational support and organisational identification $r(163) = .156, p = .046$.

3. What is the Impact of Organisational Support and Organisational Identification on Job Performance of Staff of University of Cape Coast?

Table 4. Multiple Regression

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	38.424	4.316		8.903	.000
	Organisational support	.013	.107	.009	.125	.900
	Organisational identification	.827	.145	.444	5.705	.000

a. Dependent Variable: job performance

Table 4 shows results on the test of multiple regression on how organisational support and organisational identification impact job performance. From the results, only organisational identification made positive significant predictions or impact, which means as organisational identification increases job performance increases. However, there were no significant predictions or impact relating to organisational support as $R = .459$, $R^2 = .211$, $F(3, 160) = 14.248$, $p < .001$.

Discussion of Findings

Level of Perceived Organisational Support of University Staff

The findings indicated that the majority of the staff perceived moderate levels of organisational support. This aligns with broader research on perceived organisational support (POS), which emphasises the significant impact of POS on workplace behaviour and employee outcomes. For instance, Thevanes and Savanraj (2018) reported high levels of POS, which were directly linked to increased job satisfaction. Similarly, Hashish (2020) indicated that staff members who perceived significant organisational support displayed greater organisational confidence and citizenship behaviour. According to Byrne and Hochwarter (2008), moderate levels of POS can be beneficial, particularly for employees experiencing organisational cynicism, as they tend to demonstrate improved performance compared to those experiencing either very high or very low POS. This suggests that moderate levels of support may provide a balanced environment where employees receive adequate resources and recognition without feeling excessively dependent or complacent.

Relationship between Organisational Support, Organisational Identification and Job Performance among University Staff

The study revealed a significant positive relationship between organisational identification and job performance but no direct relationship between organisational support and job performance. However, a weak but significant correlation was found between organisational support and organisational identification. These results suggest that while employees' sense of belonging to their organisation enhances their job performance, perceived organisational support may not directly influence their performance outcomes. Contrary to previous research, which generally reports a moderate positive relationship between perceived organisational support (POS) and job performance, this study found no such direct correlation. Earlier studies by Riggle et al. (2009) and Miao and Kim (2010), demonstrated that higher levels of POS contribute to increased work performance and organisational citizenship behaviour. However, Byrne et al. (2011), suggested that POS may have an indirect effect on job performance, mediated by factors like employee engagement and social exchange processes. This supports the idea that POS alone may not be sufficient to enhance job performance unless other workplace dynamics are considered.

The positive relationship between organisational support and organisational identification aligns with findings from Liu (2009), who noted that employees who feel supported by their organisation tend to internalise its values and exhibit higher levels of organisational citizenship behaviour. This suggests that when employees perceive their organisation as supportive, they are more likely to develop a stronger emotional connection to it, leading to greater workplace commitment. The strongest relationship observed in this study was between organisational identification and job performance. This supports research by Rabenu et al. (2017), Thanh et al. (2022), Issa et al. (2022), and Tanriverdi et al. (2022), who found that employees who strongly identify with their organisation tend to perform better. Employees who feel connected to their organisation are more engaged, motivated, and willing to invest discretionary effort in their roles.

Impact of Organisational Support and Organisational Identification on Job Performance of University Staff

The study revealed that organisational identification significantly predicts job performance, whereas organisational support (POS) does not have a direct impact. The results indicate that as OI increases, job

performance improves, while POS shows no significant relationship with performance. The model explains 21.1% of the variance in job performance, suggesting that OI plays a greater role in predicting employee performance than POS. The finding that POS does not significantly influence job performance contrasts with previous research, which has consistently reported a positive link between perceived support and job performance. Studies such as Wan and Saidin (2018), and Guan et al. (2014) highlight that higher organisational support enhances job satisfaction and commitment, leading to better performance. However, other research suggests that POS may work indirectly, requiring mediating factors such as engagement, job satisfaction, or affective commitment to fully translate into improved performance. This aligns with Byrne et al. (2011), who found that POS does not always have a direct impact but functions through social exchange and workplace relationships.

In contrast, OI emerged as a strong predictor of job performance, supporting the idea that employees who feel emotionally connected to their organisation are more engaged, motivated, and willing to contribute beyond their formal job roles. This finding is consistent with Lai et al. (2024), who argue that organisational identification enhances employee performance by fostering a sense of belonging and commitment. Employees who identify with their organisation are more likely to align with its goals, remain loyal, and actively contribute to its success.

The comparison between POS and OI suggests that fostering organisational identification may be more effective in driving performance than simply providing organisational support. This highlights the need for organisations to strengthen employees' emotional attachment through internal branding, leadership development, and workplace culture initiatives. Additionally, the study suggests that POS may still be valuable but requires mediating factors such as job satisfaction to fully impact performance.

Conclusion

The study's findings indicate that university staff perceive moderate levels of organisational support (POS), which aligns with research suggesting that moderate levels of POS can create a balanced work environment without leading to excessive dependence or complacency. However, POS did not directly impact job performance, which contrasts with prior studies that have reported a positive association between perceived support and employee performance. Instead, the study found that organisational identification (OI) is a significant predictor of job performance, as employees who strongly identify with their organisation tend to exhibit higher engagement, motivation, and discretionary effort in their roles.

A weak but significant correlation between POS and OI was observed, suggesting that while organisational support may not directly enhance job performance, it plays a role in strengthening employees' emotional connection to their organisation, which in turn influences their performance. These findings highlight that OI is more crucial in shaping employee behaviour and performance than POS alone.

Counselling Implications

These implications were drawn based on the results of the study.

1. Counselling initiatives should enhance employees' sense of belonging and commitment through comprehensive programmes beyond immediate aid.
2. Counsellors should organize more mentorship and career activities that align employees' personal and professional goals with the institution's objectives.
3. Counsellors should focus on leadership development, team-building, and communication across the various work places to foster inclusion as employees feel valued when engaged and often exceed expectations.

4. Counsellors should involve structured onboarding, promote diversity, and offer professional development for adapting to university culture, including career advancement paths to strengthen commitment.

5. Counsellors must address psychological and emotional barriers to job performance, such as stress, dissatisfaction, and conflicts to increase productivity.

Recommendations

The management of the University of Cape Coast should prioritise organisational identification by fostering a strong workplace culture that cultivates a sense of belonging and commitment. Leadership initiatives such as internal branding, participatory decision-making, and transparent communication can help UCC staff align with institutional values and objectives, ultimately leading to higher job performance and long-term engagement. The university Hall Management should focus on strengthening POS by providing professional development opportunities, ensuring fair treatment, and recognising staff contributions. Initiatives such as mentorship programmes, career advancement pathways, and wellness policies can help employees feel valued and motivated to perform at their best.

Given that POS may influence job performance indirectly through mediating factors like job satisfaction and employee engagement, universities should implement strategies that enhance these workplace dynamics. This can include work-life balance policies, leadership coaching, and team collaboration initiatives to help bridge the gap between perceived support and improved performance. Universities should align employees' goals with institutional objectives, ensuring that halls and administrative staff feel motivated and empowered to contribute effectively. Encouraging continuous learning, collaborative teamwork, and strong leadership support can further strengthen organisational identification and work outcomes.

Originality Statement

This work is original and that this paper has not been submitted to any other journal for consideration or so ever.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interest in this study and publication.

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Ethics Declaration and Data availability statement

The authors of this article declare that this study was conducted following ethical principles of research and that all data collected was used solely for research purposes. Data are available upon reasonable request. Requests may be submitted to the corresponding author. The data will not be made publicly available because of privacy and ethical restrictions.

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Author Contribution

Anderson: Conceptualisation & Initial Draft

Yeboah: Ethics & Methods & Data Analysis

Oduro: Literature Review & Verification

Mensah: Literature & Proofreading & Visualisation

Asamoah-Gyawu: Review Writing & Principal Investigator

Takyi: Data Analysis & Data Curation, & Principal Investigator

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All authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

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